

A Pi-Mode Extraction Scheme for the Axial B-Field Recirculating Planar Magnetron

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Abstract: *A recirculating planar magnetron (RPM), operating in the π -mode and utilizing a compact, waveguide-based extraction scheme was simulated using ICEPIC. At an applied voltage of 300 kV and B-field of 0.130T, output power was 430 MW at 43% efficiency. The oscillator was found to operate at frequency of 2.23 GHz.*

Keywords: recirculating planar magnetron; RF Extraction; HPM

Introduction

Recent work by Gilgenbach, et al., describes a new class of magnetron, namely, the recirculating planar magnetron (RPM) [1], [2]. These crossed field oscillators have a number of potential advantages, including rapid start-up, reduced cathode loading, and enhanced heat dissipation, when compared to standard cylindrical magnetron geometries.

The work described here involves using ICEPIC to computationally model the incorporation of a compact, waveguide-based extraction scheme into the axial B-field variant of the RPM described in Refs. [1] and [2]. This extraction scheme, as presented in a patent held by A. Greenwood [3], magnetically couples microwave energy from two neighboring cavities into an adjacent waveguide, assuming the magnetron is operating in the π mode.

RPM Simulations

A cross section of the RPM used in these studies is depicted in Figure 1. The sets of two neighboring magnetron cavities coupled to adjacent waveguides are visible in this figure. The waveguides are oriented such that the propagation axis of the guide is along the Z-axis. Figure 1 (b) shows an orthogonal projection to that of Figure 1 (a), centered at $Y = 0$

cm, in which the waveguides, apertures, and perfectly matched waveguide loads (PML) are visible. Also visible in Figure 1 are particle phase space data (shown in green) at $t = 300$ ns for a simulation in which a 300 kV potential was applied across the 2 cm wide anode-cathode gap and a uniform 0.130 T magnetic field was applied along the Z-axis.

As noted in Figure 1 (a), the waveguides include capacitive ridges. This is done to increase the bandwidth of the waveguide to allow for reduced waveguide widths which, in turn, allow for reduced phase velocities for the RF wave in the cavity. For reference, if a non-ridged waveguide were used and operated just above cutoff, the wave phase velocity would be just above $c/2$, which leads to a reduced maximum theoretical efficiency, when compared with standard relativistic magnetrons that typically have phase velocities ranging from $0.24c$ to $0.34c$ [4], [5]. For the present simulations, each waveguide has a width of 4.8 cm, a height of 2.5 cm and ridge radii of 1.0cm, resulting in a cutoff frequency below 2 GHz.

Plots for current, voltage, output power, and efficiency for the $B=0.130$ T case are shown in Figure 2. In this plot, upstream and downstream power for each of the 10 waveguides was summed. As shown in Ref. 3, waveguide shorts can be placed in the waveguide to direct all power upstream or downstream. Steady state power in the $B=1.30$ T case was approximately 430 MW and efficiency was approximately 43%. Increasing the magnetic field to 0.135 T was found to reduce output power to 330 MW but increase efficiency to 55%. Decreasing the applied magnetic field to 0.125 T increased output power to 520 MW but reduced efficiency to 35%.

Figure 1. Cross sections of the simulation geometry and particle cloud, including the X-Y plane (a) and the X-Z plane (b).

Figure 2. Plots of current, voltage, power, and efficiency for the $B = 0.130$ T case.

A FFT spectrum of the RF electric field across one of the magnetron cavities is displayed in Figure 3. The operating frequency of the device is 2.23GHz, resulting in a π -mode phase velocity of approximately $0.37c$. As shown in Figure 3, the output spectrum of the device does not show evidence of any strong competing modes.

Figure 3. Hot tube frequency spectrum for the $B = 0.130$ T case.

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